

The Philosophy Behind Violence Against Married Women: Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: Married women in Pakistan in general and traditional communities in Gilgit-Baltistan in particular are often victims of violence in many forms and manifestations from their intimate partners and family members. On the other hand, certain Gilgit-Baltistan communities give women equal opportunities in terms of employment and education. To enhance knowledge of the notion underpinning violence against "married women," this research centers on significant participants who experienced physical, psychological, and sexual abuse inside the context. A referral, snowball sampling strategy was employed by the researchers to determine which respondents were most relevant for data gathering. To gather detailed information for a thematic analysis of the data, in-depth interviews were conducted. The findings revealed that the dynamics behind violence against married women is influenced by a deeply established and seemingly embedded patriarchal socio-cultural milieu. Lack of education, difficult financial circumstances, unsatisfactory marriages, problems with socio-cultural norms, the belief that women are less than men, and other factors have been identified as the main causes of physical, psychological, and sexual violence against women. To lessen violence against women, it is recommended that women and girls receive education from pre-school through university.

Keywords: Physical Abuse, Emotional Violence, Psychological Violence, Cultural Norms, Conservative Societies, Lack of Education.

[Introduction](#)

[Materials and Methods](#)

[Results and Discussions](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[Acknowledgments](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

In Pakistan, violence against married women is a prevalent and deeply established issue that still has an impact on a large number of women's lives. Domestic violence episodes, including physical, emotional, and sexual abuse, persist despite legislative protections and awareness. Economic reliance, cultural standards, and patriarchal beliefs

all frequently play a role in the persistence of violence against women. Furthermore, because of social stigmas and barriers to reporting, victims find it challenging to access support services and seek help.

A kind of superiority complex and psychological problem with men in male-dominated societies is essentially what drives men to harm some women, especially their wives, in various ways and under various circumstances. These include factors such as gender, cultural norms, myths, taboos, economic conditions, and social status, to name a few. But it appears to be a worldwide problem that affects both developed and developing nations (Wemrell, 2023; WHO, 2019). Finding context-specific solutions to these kinds of problems requires identifying the dominant thought patterns and socio-cultural, political, economic, and other settings within a given society that contribute significantly to the prevalence of violence against women. As a result, this study in the setting of Gilgit-Baltistan, one of the world's most mountainous regions, will add to the body of literature from a place where studies on similar themes still appear to be lacking for a variety of reasons.

According to Schrubbe et al. (2023) the term Violence Against Women (VAW) refers to a variety of coercive acts that are sexual, psychological, and physical that male individuals or partners in society perpetrate against women. In addition, the United Nations General Assembly defines VAW broadly, including acts that are likely to cause bodily, sexual, or psychological harm to women as well as any type of gender-based violence. Threats, coercion, and loss of liberty are all included in this description and can happen in both public and private settings (Tarar, Safdar, & Hassan, 2017; Ahmed & Tarannum, 2019). As a result, VAW is a socially, emotionally, and physically sanctioned form of discrimination against women that damages their feelings and emotions and abuses them psychologically, sexually, physically, etc. This implies that any type of encounter or contact that causes women to feel harassed and insecure in their lives is considered VAW.

A review of the literature on the subject of VAW makes it clear that, while the problem has been in some form over the world for some time, it was not given much attention as a concern until around three decades ago (Alhabib, 2010; Izmirli et al, 2014). Over the course of several decades of global efforts, VAW did, however, progressively garner significant attention, and today it is regarded as one of the major issues facing the societies in which it exists (Wands & Mirzoev, 2021). This suggests that in societies including Gilgit-Baltistan where women are less powerful and are not aware of their rights, VAW is a significant issue that requires urgent attention. Furthermore, it is imperative to view VAW as a field of study to explore deeper inside into perceptions, beliefs, myths and taboos associated with it to address the issues with contextual solutions and contribute towards building a healthy egalitarian society.

Women in Pakistan frequently face shockingly high rates of violence, and the government offers little assistance in this regard. Abbas, Bilal, and Rashid (2022) estimate that between 70 and 90 percent of Pakistani women are victims of domestic abuse. Married Pakistani women report a third or more of them having been physically abused by their husbands. According to official data, the percentage of Pakistani women working is only 22%. The National Report on the Status of Women in Pakistan (2023) states that out of

married women aged 15 to 49, 23% reported physical abuse, 26% emotional abuse, and 5% sexual abuse at the hands of their husbands or intimate partners. There was a somewhat greater rate of violence in rural than in urban areas. Furthermore, among women with no education, all forms of violence were more common, whereas among women with greater education, they were less common. Compared to 16% of women from higher economic situations, 28% of women facing multidimensional poverty reported having experienced physical or sexual assault. Comparably, domestic abuse is often written off as a personal, family matter, which causes the judiciary and law enforcement to discriminate against and ignore women. Furthermore, it appears to be a blatant violation of fundamental human rights, as guaranteed by international law, to portray religion as an excuse for women's abuse and domestic violence on the one hand, and their denial of justice on the other (Abbas, Biolal, & Rashid, 2022).

Women in Gilgit-Baltistan (GB), Pakistan, like in other parts of the world, face violence on a daily basis on a variety of levels, especially from their life partners (Akter, 2020; Din, Fatima, & Aziz, 2018; Wands & Mirzoev, 2021). But in conservative societies, this kind of violence in this situation is not seen as problematic that is itself a very serious matter. Furthermore, the majority of women in such societies in GB seem to defend this violence as the rights of their men. This is a result of their lack of education, exposure to the outside world, increased financial dependence on their parents and spouses, ignorance of their own rights, and other factors (Khan & Hussain, 2008; Khan & Islam, 2018).

The researchers advise individuals, regardless of gender, to think about the ideas and actions that lead them to hurt other people. But it seems that women in these societies within male dominated rigid cultural settings are more denied access to their fundamental rights, and they require empowerment to overcome the obstacles they experience on a daily basis. This cultural dominance results in the social rights of women being infringed. According to Babur (2007) and Toni-Uebari & Inusa (2009), women's physical, educational, and economic well-being are negatively impacted by conventional male-centric views and inferiority complexes. Murshid and Critelli (2020) assert that strengthening women and attending to their problems in Pakistan can help reduce discrimination, contempt, and the amount of women who pass away in violent accidents. Thus, the purpose of this study is to explore married women's opinions of violence against women as well as taboos, cultural norms, and other factors that encourage violence in the society.

2. Materials and Methods

As part the qualitative research methodology, the researchers identified significant individual informants using the maximum variations snowball sampling procedure (Parker, Scott, & Geddes, 2019). This approach is effective in summarizing the variety of experiences that occur among members of "a hard-to-reach populations" in a given community (Parker et al., 2019, p. 4). When it comes to overcoming socio-cultural taboos that prevent researchers from discussing these kinds of topics in public, this is one of the most practical strategies. Consequently, snowball sampling is a very practical and secure method of contacting the appropriate informant in order to collect the necessary data (Slabbert, 2017). Thus, it was utilized to gather data on the level of violence against married

women in some of the most conservative societies in GB, where these women face abuse and domestic violence. For that purpose, the selection criterion was set with the following two conditions, i.e., a) respondents are married and belong to some of the most conservative societies of GB, and b) the respondent must have faced domestic violence from her husband and/or from the family members.

As a result, just fifteen (15) women could be found who voluntarily consented to take part in the study and share their stories with the researchers. In order to explore the philosophy behind VAW as well as their own experiences as victims, the researchers formally obtained their consent, assured the participants about the confidentiality of the data, and let them know that they could even end the interview at any time if they felt uncomfortable.

Afterwards, the women from some of the most conservative societies in GB took part in semi-structured in-depth interviews with the researchers. There were two components to the interview guide that the researchers created. Enumerating the participants' socioeconomic situation and demographic profiles such as the number of children, years of marriage, household income, children's schooling, and health concerns was the main goal of the first portion. In order to better understand the mentalities and ideologies underlying domestic violence against married women in the chosen area, the interview guide's second portion included questions.

An average of forty-five minutes was spent in each interview discussing the participants' experiences and opinions regarding VAW. After the interviews, the researchers shared the final transcriptions of the interviews in order to obtain clarifications and made some adjustments in two cases.

In order to thoroughly investigate the problem at hand, the gathered data went through a rigorous process of thematic analysis and interpretation. A clear hierarchy of headings and sub-themes was established for the identified themes. All interview replies were interpreted, with each interviewee's response being matched to the appropriate categories or topics as codes. After reviewing, researching, and renaming the themes emerged (Braun & Clarke, 2006, Clarke & Braun, 2017), the final themes were presented.

3. Results and Discussions

The study's findings suggest that a number of factors rooted in the sociocultural norms of conservative countries play a significant role in influencing men's use of violence against their partners and even other female family members. These conclusions highlighted male control over women, women's ignorance and lack of knowledge, women's response to and tolerance for abuse, families' attitudes of marriages including understanding couples, and ways to put an end to VAW. The following significant study results were broken down into sections and then discussed in light of the main findings, the literature was reviewed, and the authors' opinions were given.

3.1. Male Dominance Over Women

In this milieu, some societies display patriarchal sociocultural, dogmatic, and economic backgrounds that lead to the mistreatment and marginalization of women in a variety of contexts (Babur, 2007; Hussain et al., 2020). Several studies have repeatedly shown that women experience greater levels of marginalization and subordination in such male-dominated cultures (Bhatta et al., 2021; MICS-GB, 2016–17).

The behavior in inquiry is widespread in GB, especially in some of the most conservative areas where the proportion of educated women is significantly lower than in any other district. In the joint family system, where the majority of families live, women are marginalized in the family environment, imposed restrictions on women and have no say in decision-making. One of the 54-year women was this to say,

I lived with my spouse for a long time, and throughout that time, I experienced abuse from his family members including himself. My spouse used to hit me for small violations, and I had mental stress from the entire family as a result of having a child very late in our marriage... although my father's house is not far from mine, I am only able to visit him on special occasions once a year.

She further added, "When I argued with my husband..., who runs a small business and is also addicted to alcohol, he returned home late, beat me, and threatened to get married again."

Studies have shown that in traditional societies in developing nations, such as Pakistan, beating women, threatening to marry another woman, and honor killings have become serious concerns (Lansford et al., 2020). Unfortunately, real measures to stop these crimes and alter the perceptions of those who support VAW in all its manifestations have not been sufficiently implemented (Khatib et al., 2020). A serious flaw in the state's operation is its inability to confront and outlaw these kinds of activities in all of their forms (Bhatta et al., 2021).

Based on the literature and existing practices, the researchers concluded that the state has failed in educating men to change the way they think and to treat women as equal and important members of society. Women's suffering is therefore unimportant to complex, male-dominated communities that are unaware of women's rights.

3.2. Lack of Education and Awareness

Studies show that in conservative countries, there is a strong connection between the VAW and low levels of education and ignorance of women's rights (Esposito et al., 2020). Because of ingrained sociocultural norms, a considerable number of women in some of the most conservative societies in GB are lower economic status and cannot attend primary education in formal educational institutions. One study subject succinctly described her experience, saying,

Since my father passed away when I was five years old and we moved in with my uncle, I have never attended school. I married the son of one of my uncle's friends when I was just 13 years old. He was employed in a nearby hospital as a Grade 1 (Chaprasi). He

was under contract at the moment and felt irritated... and he used to consistently beat me. I used to feel emotionally stressed out by his telling me to have a divorce. Even with three kids now, I still have to deal with his aggression in front of them.

Moreover, she further expressed, "I am unable to attend formal schooling; I can only read the Holy Quran. I think educated women are capable of opposing domestic violence.

Another woman shared her opinion in response to a question, saying, "In our social structure, people only want to educate their male children and spend their little resources on male education." She went on to say, "I believe we should also educate our female children." Because I am an uneducated woman, I am the target of abuse from my husband's family. I never marry someone who is uneducated if I have education. Similarly, yet another participant expressed her views in these words,

Before I became a mother, my spouse used to call names and hit me frequently. My son is younger than my daughters. We had three kids; I became pregnant relatively late in my marriage, and during that time, I experienced domestic abuse on a regular basis, both physically and psychologically. Following the children's arrival, the level of violence dropped. My spouse gets upset with me when I disagree and he sometimes hits me violently. Education, in my opinion, is crucial for women's empowerment and for equipping them to resist assault. I would never get married, work, and lead a happy life if I had the education. As a woman, I believe that one of the main causes of violence is a lack of education. Our female children need to be taught to oppose violence.

Another participant, a victim of early marriage, gave the following description of the kind of violence she has encountered in her life while sharing her tale.

I married at the age of twelve and never attended school. I suffered from many forms of abuse and anguish from both my in-laws and my husband for a considerable amount of my married life. I was physically and emotionally stressed at an early age by my in-laws and spouse. In the beginning of my marriage, my mother-in-law used to hit me for little disagreements. But my father-in-law treated me with respect and decency. I felt safe in the house while my father-in-law was there. My family lets me see my mother and father after six or seven months. Getting married is similar to being imprisoned, with the husband having all authority over the wife.

Research indicates that VAW occurs in many societies for a range of causes in many different forms (Abramsky et al., 2011; WHO, 2013; Hussain et al, 2020). Nonetheless, in these conservative communities, ignorance of women's rights appears to be the primary cause. Many innocent women can be protected from domestic abuse if the state shows concern for the lives of these and other underprivileged groups in society.

Moreover, insufficient progress has been made by governments, such as Pakistan's, in empowering women by ensuring that they have fair access to high-quality education and encouraging communal participation. Accordingly, the perpetuation of VAW and the maintenance of male dominance have been facilitated by the existing patriarchal social structure in conjunction with the dearth of educational opportunities and forced early marriages. In some of the more traditional societies in GB men have a strong sense of

authority over women, which is ingrained in their cultural values and way of thinking. Strong traditions of masculine honor—a form of gender discrimination—are likewise ingrained in the beliefs and customs of these communities. This seems to be one of the main issues with VAW in these communities.

3.3. Women's Patience at Abuse and Their Response

It is peculiar that married girls' fathers and mothers counsel them to endure whatever hardships they encounter in their husbands' homes, given the sociocultural backdrop of conservative societies in general and developing nations like Pakistan in particular (MICS 2016–17). The pressure placed on women by society and parents' silence over the VAW seem to encourage men to mistreat women in their roles as spouses, daughters, sisters, and so on.

I had no choice but to bear and tolerate the abuse, said one research participant, describing her experience of violence and her parents' response. Parents, or females, have taught us to put up with the abuse of our husbands and their families in order to preserve our reputation in the community and preserve our culture and social structure. Moreover, she added that, however, my spouse used to call me derogatory names, verbally attack me about things I can't discuss in public, and punch me in the face over trivial domestic disputes. And sometimes he acts in this way to make me feel inferior to him in front of his family. I am therefore completely tired of my life.

In addition, numerous other participants expressed their extreme frustration with the so-called cultural standards of society, which prevent them from telling their parents and other loved ones about incidents of violence against them in order to ask for assistance. They think that if they do it and their parents react negatively, everybody would laugh at them. It's one of the reasons daughters who experience abuse in their husbands' families after marriage choose to keep quiet about it.

"At my home, I am now used to bearing all kinds of abuse including physical, emotional, and psychological etc. from in laws," stated one participant, summarizing her situation. "I'm supporting my brother's education because my father can't afford it, and my in-laws don't like it," she continued. "My husband is more understanding and supportive, but my mother-in-law has a problem with me."

The literature supports the participants' narratives, demonstrating that VAW is a significant problem that mostly affects societies with poor educational attainment, a male-dominated culture, and a perception of women as slaves (Wands & Mirzoev, 2021; Mavisakalyan & Rammohan, 2021).

In this case, it appears that the government, social activists, religious leaders, and other groups are silent on these kinds of societal issues; therefore, they must work together to end VAW. It is feasible to create an egalitarian society where everyone has an equal opportunity to benefit from education and take part honorably in familial, social, and political activities through coordinated efforts and common wisdom.

3.4. Families' Reactions over Marriages with Couples' Understanding

As boys and girls come to an agreement on the matter of marriage, it has been noted that in the majority of traditional societies, marriage is not regarded as a dignified act and is instead viewed as a form of crime or a sin (Perveen & Malik, 2020). Relatively few respondents said their parents arranged their marriages, which they eventually decided to go along with. These marriages led to discrimination against women and couples in the households, with the in-laws mistreating the newlyweds and demeaning them as individuals. One of the respondent told her narrative in the following ways,

My spouse and I chose to get married of our own free will, which is why my in-laws don't like me as much. Despite my beauty and our understanding, I endure psychological stress and abuse from my in-laws. My mother-in-law kept me confined within the four walls while granting her daughter—my husband's sister—freedom.

She went on to say that,

My spouse and I decided to get married, and subsequently, our family acknowledged this decision. I had a variety of challenges, problems, and abuse from my in-laws during the early years of my marriage. Because my husband's family and I are from different backgrounds, it was really challenging for me to understand the in-laws when I first got married. Cultural norms make it difficult for my in-laws to accept our love marriage, even if they first accepted it for the sake of their son. They later on repeatedly mistreated me psychologically and emotionally throughout my life.

One more participant shared her opinions about these worlds. During the first roughly 10 years of my marriage, my family was joined. My husband's sister and my mother-in-law are at odds with me. My spouse was a driver, and his absence from the house caused him to become tense. She went on to say that,

My spouse wasn't adequately concentrate on his career because we were constantly having issues at home. I put up with his occasional severe beatings of me because I care about my kids' future. At the time, my spouse and I had bought a little house in Gilgit. However, there was a dispute in the house, so he quit his work and sold the property. We now regret doing such things. Domestic violence, in my opinion, has an effect on a person's mental health in addition to causing physical pain or harm. I think, mental torment, tension, misery, etc., are the worst forms of pain or suffering caused by violence... why I am treated like a destructive, nasty beast. Every now and then, these problems and anxieties run through the mind, causing disturbance, sleeplessness, improper eating, and an ongoing state of suffering. I think, the situation lowers society's level of self-esteem and confidence.

Studies confirm the opinions of research participants that VAW results in time wastage and financial loss in addition to psychological or bodily injury to victims and their family (Kang et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2020). According to a few of the female respondents, the VAW caused them numerous hardships. She told another relative girl's story.

One of our relative, a girl in my father's village has been accused of being raped by a powerful family member. Nearly ten years have passed after this incident, and the girl is still not married and does not face the society. Nobody wants to marry her because of the stigmas society has attached to her persona. Her parents are no longer with her, and she currently resides at her brother's house.

Due to these kinds of societal and cultural taboos, women endure numerous difficulties and various sorts of violence including sexual harassment that endanger their entire lives. The society's criminal males take pleasure in their position of authority and are not subject to any negative consequences.

3.5. Overcome the VAW

Every year, millions of women and girls experience sexual, physical, psychological, and emotional abuse and harassment at the hands of an intimate partner and his family at home, in society, and at work (Khaliq & Ahmad, 2021; Wands & Mirzoev, 2021). Furthermore, according to Saeed et al. (2017), VAW and girls can exist in any civilization that is going through a time of conflict and unequal involvement in day-to-day activities. They are not restricted to any particular society, culture, religion, or group. It's interesting to note that one participant argued that "extending equal access to education to women can empower them to overcome barriers and reduce the likelihood of violence." "In our village, it has been observed that women with limited or no access to education are more likely to be abused," said a different participant. One more participant expressed, "I believe that education can help husband and wife to develop better understanding and reduce violence." This suggests that VAW is a major problem in conservative developing-nation where there is a dearth of education and knowledge about women's rights. Women's education can be a tool for improving husband-wife relationships and reducing violent behaviors.

VAW has a lot of negative repercussions on society. To cite a few, it undermines women's worth, confidence, and respect from society; it damages their reproductive and general health; it lowers economic output; and it may even result in divorce (Qamar & Faizan, 2021). Furthermore, all forms of violence have a big impact on a society's capacity to uphold security, preserve peace, and grow economically (Bhatta et al., 2021). Most participants said that violence makes women feel insecure, damages their physical and mental health, hurts their finances, creates strained relationships, and, in the worst situations, results in separation. According to an educated female teacher,

VAW obviously breaks moral standards and human rights. Intimate relationships are impacted, mental health is disturbed, and mistrust is increased. It's important to keep in mind, though, that blaming women primarily for defying their husbands' commands oversimplifies the issue. While following their husbands' instructions can make marriages operate more smoothly and reduce conflicts of interest, it's crucial to note that the majority of domestic violence is brought on by miscommunications and arguments between spouses over specific matters.

This illustrates the enormous social, moral, psychological, and financial toll it exacts, having an adverse effect on victims' lives as well as the societies in which they live. In a

violent environment, women are unable to reach their full potential in terms of achieving their personal, professional, and organizational goals. Therefore, it would appear that building mutual understanding through listening to one another and attending to needs, goals, and desires within their cultural contexts is essential to reducing violence.

In some conservative and even so-called liberal countries where male supremacy is upheld by long-standing social structures, it is customary to discourage women from participating in decision-making processes. As one participant put it, "we the women are not asked while taking decisions in family matters". Furthermore, most women seem to contend that decisions are primarily forced upon them based on what males deem to be correct and that they are not respected in the decision-making process. Reducing violence and fostering healthy relationships can be achieved by granting women equal status in domestic affairs (Ali et al., 2020), raising knowledge of gender dynamics between the sexes, and including women in life decision-making.

This means that VAW can be reduced in developing countries like Pakistan by educating the public, increasing public awareness, and preserving economic stability through granting equal opportunities and respect to all members of society, regardless of gender, in all spheres of life. By doing this, it will be possible to reduce the number of domestic conflicts, which will improve relationships and raise the level of life in a respectful and peaceful community.

4. Conclusion

It is evident from the backdrop of Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan in general, and conservative societies in particular that intimate partners and their families frequently utilize violence against married women in a variety of ways. One of the causes of the practices of violence against married women is the mentality of the male element of society, which ultimately leads to the violence. Other causes include issues with the male superiority complex, social taboos, restricted opportunities including educational and economic, and ignorance of women's rights.

Under such circumstance, the study discovered a noteworthy incidence of domestic violence among married women, particularly in areas where women are excluded from employment and educational prospects, and are also unable to participate in family decision-making, among other reasons that contribute to their experience of violence. The findings demonstrate the pressing need to combat violence against married women, even in the absence of updated statistics in the context.

Furthermore, males in conservative societies receive greater parental attention than girls, which contributes to the neglect of the female population and makes them later victims of violence. But it seems that women who bear children later in life and don't have any boys are more likely to become victims of domestic abuse, which puts women's safety at risk. Such VAW is recognized as a grave instance of discrimination based on gender and as a human rights violation. Creating equal opportunities for women to access high-quality education and support themselves through economic empowerment, as well as challenging

socio-cultural norms like early marriages, social taboos, and other forms of discrimination, are necessary to reduce violence against married women in conservative societies.

According to the study, developing an egalitarian society that guarantees the equal participation of male and female social groups and fosters the ideas of respect for all and hate for none in the context of peaceful coexistence is heavily dependent on collective wisdom. Coexistence of this nature can help societies in developing nations like Pakistan flourish sustainably.

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